

Co-authors: Alexandre Robert, Fabio Balli, Nadja Moser, Nadine Henschel– June 22, 2023

Contributors: Martin Reiser, David Risse, Quentin Adler

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Towards a Planetary Health Solidarity Initiative

The territory is our body. It is also the location of the natural resources and social wealth of our communities. We are the guardians of the territories, of the rivers, of the continuity of life.

Ana Maria Hernandez,¹ land defender

We need the political will to forge a peace pact with nature.

Antonio Guterres,² UN Secretary-General

Background

As negotiations for the Pandemic Treaty continue at the WHO,³ the current focus is primarily centred on a conventional approach of global health security. It lacks an integrated approaches to planetary health* governance, promoting coherence across life-preserving initiatives and agreements.⁴ Citizens across the globe⁵⁻⁶ as well as international expert groups such as the UNGA,⁷ IPCC,⁸ IPBES⁹ or The Lancet Countdown,¹⁰ are clear that **systemic transformations are needed to prevent the consequences of human-led damage to Earth's ecosystems**. More importantly, little attention is given to social, legal, political and economic structural drivers of glocal* environmental system change ([Annex I](#)).¹¹

In contrast to the state-led approach to global health security, a planetary health solidarity* initiative takes a cross-border and transdisciplinary approach led by citizens across the globe.¹²⁻¹³ It emphasises a sovereign, cosmo-local* valuation of our well-being and health (promotion, prevention and regeneration), and relies on building trust and confidence to foster collective and individual resilience. Having overcome the most severe stage of the Covid-19 pandemic management, and the resulting exacerbation of inequalities,¹⁴⁻¹⁵ the current negotiations of a Pandemic treaty offers a window of opportunity: to promote a more equitable and sustainable approach for the future global health policy based on planetary health. **This should, by design, increase embodied solidarity across humans, and foster the cohabitation of plural perspectives and practices,¹⁶⁻¹⁷ as recommended by UNESCO.¹⁸**

The idea: a Planetary Health Solidarity Initiative

As States and the World Health Assembly are failing to implement systemic transformation required to preserve a liveable planet for the current and future generations, a **coalition of diverse people from around the world are committed to promoting planetary health, developing a bottom-up proposal: The Planetary Health Solidarity Initiative.**

The initiative aims to shift the paradigm from global health security to planetary health solidarity through a citizen-led, bottom-up approach ([Annex II](#)). **Rather than relying solely on government or institutional actors to lead the way, this initiative seeks to leverage the commons, collective knowledge, creativity, and energy of converging glocal communities networks.** This initiative should ensure a common understanding and collective engagement among the coalition partners

themselves. The desired outcome is a draft of the Planetary Health Solidarity agenda by 2024 and the launch of Planetary Health projects, both to emerge from a consensus in our community.

As many citizens and institutions aim to increase the role of communities in decision-making and research, the festival 'taking care together' provides the ideal platform to kick start the initiative and share the concept with the global health community.¹⁹

June 22, 2023: Bringing people together to create a manifesto and launch the initiative

To bring this initiative to life, a participatory webinar will be held online.

Title	Toward a Planetary Health Solidarity Initiative - Participatory webinar
Aim	Participatory drafting of a manifesto* (and possibly a policy brief or call), which will consist of a set of principles and recommendations for planetary health solidarity (Annex III). Official launch of the Planetary Health Solidarity Initiative.
Date	Thursday, June 22, 2023
Time	14:00 to 16:00 CET / 22:00 to 23:59 JST / 9 to 11 am EDT
Where	Online, link sent after registration
Design	Method to collective elaborate and agree among each and every participant ²⁰ Part of the festival 'taking care together' and the 'oonehealth' participatory study ²¹
Hosts	Alexandre Robert, Fabio Balli, Nadine Henschel, Joanna Wagner
Participants	Up to 60 individuals committed to preserve the Earth's ecosystems including people from the global and planetary health communities
Registration	Free of cost, required at https://www.openvillage.ch/nature

Next steps

- After June 2023, Presentation
 - o The manifesto/policy brief will be submitted and presented to the WHO Director General by the youngest planetary health ambassador, who will lead to a consultation with the World Health Assembly (WHA) organising committee.
 - o An article will be submitted to a relevant journal.
- November 2023, Design of agenda
 - o Finished draft of proposal for a Planetary health solidarity agenda.
- May 2024, Launch
 - o Launch of the Planetary health solidarity agenda during the WHA.

Definitions

- **Cosmo-localism:** “an alternative framework for collaborative production. It aims to create resilience locally by sharing resources globally as ‘digital commons’. As Ramos notes: ‘In very basic terms cosmo-localism describes the dynamic potentials of our emerging globally distributed knowledge and design commons in conjunction with the emerging (high and low tech) capacity for localised production of value’” ([Schismenos and Niaros, 2020](#)).
- **Glocal:** “describing the seamless integration between the local and global; the comprehensive connectedness produced by travel, business, and communications; willingness and ability to think globally and act locally” ([Oxford Reference, 2023](#)).
- **Manifesto:** “a written statement of the beliefs, aims, and policies of an organization” ([Cambridge Dictionary, 2023](#)).
- **Planetary Health:** “a solutions-oriented, transdisciplinary approach and social movement focused on analyzing and addressing the impacts of human disruptions to Earth's natural systems on human health and all life on Earth” ([Planetary Health Alliance, 2021](#)).
- **Solidarity:** “agreement between and support for the members of a group” ([Cambridge Dictionary, 2023](#)); “Global challenges must be managed in a way that distributes the costs and burdens fairly in accordance with basic principles of equity and social justice. Those who suffer or who benefit least deserve help from those who benefit most” ([UN Millennium Declaration, 2000](#)).

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Annex I – Examples of structural drivers of global environmental system change

climate change, environmental degradation, land use, privatization of assets, destruction of natural habitats and ecosystems and loss of biodiversity, rapid urbanization and demographic growth. These drivers lead to growth in population exposure, vulnerability and gaps in prevention, preparedness and responses for epidemics.

Annex II – An interdisciplinary approach to identifying

source: www.pandemictreaty.net

Annex III – Key features of the initiative, to be discussed and agreed upon

Global health security	Planetary health solidarity
State-dependent	State independent
Led by state officials	Led by a diversity of citizens across the globe
Planification of security based on control and measure (fear)	Emergence of solidarity based on mutual support and collective wisdom (trust)
Stewardship of private goods funded by public	Stewardship of commons
Living organisms as a threat to control	Living organisms as a chance to thrive
Focus on protection and response	Focus on well-being, health promotion, prevention and regeneration
Surveillance & Control	Trust & Confidence
Passive response	Pro-active resilience

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